

Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the current ratio using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the current ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the current ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the current ratio using Library Research. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 33 journal publications regarding the current ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the Current ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 92 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 12 topics around the influence of the current ratio and 1 topic about the determinants of the current ratio. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around current ratio, so that future researchers can find out research gaps about current ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around current ratios that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Current ratio; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

The development of the current ratio in the banking industry can be influenced by various factors, including economic growth, interest rates, credit risk and risk management policies (Andhitiyara, 2020). An increase in the current ratio is usually considered profitable because it shows that the bank has more current assets that can be used to meet short-term obligations. However, a significant increase could also indicate that the bank may be facing liquidity problems (Romli, 2022).

The current ratio policy in banking is an important aspect to ensure liquidity and sufficient cash funds held by the bank. The current ratio is a financial ratio that measures a bank's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations using assets that can be cashed in a short time (Saggaf, 2016). Usually, banks will set a current ratio policy that reflects risk tolerance and capital requirements in accordance with the business strategy and banking regulations applicable in that country (Daulay, 2021). Current ratio policies can vary from one bank to another depending on factors such as risk profile, business strategy, types of products offered, and regulatory requirements (Wati, 2018). In general, a high current ratio indicates that the bank has good liquidity and is able to meet its short-term obligations easily. However, a current ratio that is too high can also indicate that the bank has too many unproductive or inefficient assets, so it does not provide optimal results for shareholders (Nur'aidawati, 2018). On the other hand, a current ratio that is too low can indicate a liquidity problem, where the bank may face difficulties in

meeting its short-term obligations. This could potentially cause financial instability and reduce the trust of customers and other stakeholders (Lautama, 2019). The importance of the current ratio policy is to ensure that the bank has the right balance between sufficient liquidity to meet its short-term obligations and optimal use of its assets. Banks must actively manage their current ratio by paying attention to changes in liquidity needs and risks associated with their business operations (Lieony, 2022).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around current ratios in Islamic and conventional banking using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publication of a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from Sinta accredited national journal. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around the current ratio, so that future researchers can find out research gaps. about the current ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around current ratios that are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Current ratio is a financial ratio used in banking analysis to measure a bank's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations (Mambrisau, 2015). This ratio describes the relationship between current assets (assets that can be quickly converted into cash) and current liabilities (debts that are due within one year). The formula for the current ratio is: $\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Debt}}$ (Ismanandar, 2016). Current assets include cash, short-term investments, loans that mature within one year, accounts receivable, and merchandise inventory that can be sold in the near future. Current Debt (current liabilities) include short-term bank debt, debt to customers, business debt, accrued expenses, and other short-term liabilities (Harianja, 2022).

Bibliometric studies are an analytical approach that uses quantitative methods to study the characteristics of scientific publications, such as journals, articles, or conferences in a particular field. This study focuses on quantitative measurements of publication patterns, development history, and relationships between authors, institutions, and research topics (Dubyna et al., 2022). VOSviewer is one of the software that is often used in bibliometric studies. This software is used to visualize and analyze scientific collaboration networks, involving authors, institutions, keywords, or research subject. VOSviewer utilizes bibliographic data, such as information from resource indexes such as Scopus or Web of Science, to produce informative and interactive visualizations. Using VOSviewer, researchers can identify collaboration patterns between authors or institutions, describe developments and trends in research topics, and analyze the influence and relationships between various elements in a particular academic domain. This software provides interesting network visualizations, such as cluster maps, co-cluster graphs, or distance graphs. In addition, VOSviewer also supports text analysis to identify the most relevant keywords or the most important concepts in a research area. With VOSviewer, researchers can extract new insights from bibliographic data and analyze trends and collaboration patterns in scientific research (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a research method carried out by collecting, analyzing and synthesizing various relevant literature sources in a particular field

of knowledge. The purpose of a Library Research is to present a comprehensive understanding of the research topic being studied. In a Library Research study, researchers identify relevant literature sources such as scientific journals, articles, books, and theses related to their research topic. After that, they read, analyze, and combine the information found from these sources. At the analysis stage, researchers will evaluate and interpret information found in the literature to see trends, important findings, and differences in research approaches or methods used by previous researchers. In this case, a Library Research study can help researchers to identify knowledge gaps, weaknesses, or gaps that exist in research that has been conducted previously. The results of a Library Research study often take the form of a systematic review or synthesis of related research conducted previously. It can provide a strong and comprehensive knowledge base for researchers to continue their research or develop theoretical frameworks. Library Research studies have an important role in scientific research, because they can help researchers to understand the existing theoretical context, identify shortcomings in previous research, explore emerging themes, and develop more specific and relevant research questions (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is the current ratio. The type of data used is data secondary. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on current ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " current ratio " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the current ratio using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around the current ratio using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the current ratio using a Library Research.

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications around Current Ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 33 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2013 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding the Current ratio by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2013	1	2018	2	2021	8

2015	1	2019	3	2022	8
2016	2	2020	2	2023	2
2017	3				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping Research Topics around Current ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking using VOSviewer Bibliometric Studies

Article search results in the Perish/Harzing software are exported in format RIS (Research Information Systems), then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around the Current ratio.

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

VOSViewer software visualization results regarding research development maps regarding current ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 6 clusters and 92 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1 consists of 28 topic items, namely: assets, good, bei, Indonesian stock exchange, current ratio, debt, der, earnings, Indonesian securities, equity, equity ratio, ftable, stock price, Indonesia, method, influence of current ratio, the influence of debt, company, return, roa, roe, share, is significant on stock prices, spss, tattoo, total asset turnover, test, f test.
- Cluster 1 consists of 25 topic items, namely: annual financial statement, annual report, company, conventional banking company, corporate social responsibility, CSR, empirical evidence, environmental aspect, investment, investor, level, multiple linear regression, quantitative research, research, sample, secondary data, significant effect, stock price, sustainability, t test, technique, time, variable, way, wwwidxcoid.
- Cluster 1 consists of 16 topic items, namely: banking company, bond rating, data, data analysis method, dividend payout ratio, financial statement, firm

size, form, influence, leverage, multiple linear regression, population, purposive sampling, sampling technique, size, study.

- Cluster 1 consists of 12 topic items, namely: analytical method, deposit ratio, effect, factor, idx, ldr, liquidity, loan, multiple regression analysis, observation period, profitability, quantitative method.
- Cluster 1 consists of 10 topic items, namely: banks, debt equity ratio, debt ratio, hypothesis, impact, Indonesian stock exchange, banking companies, purposive sampling method, relationship, significant impact.
- Cluster 1 consists of 1 topic item, namely: bopo.

Mapping Research Topics around the Influence of the Current Ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking using Library Research

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 12 influences of the current ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The influence of the current ratio on CAR can occur through two main channels: (1) Liquidity and its influence on CAR: A high current ratio indicates that the bank has good liquidity, which can help the bank in dealing with emergency situations, such as large withdrawals by customers or market instability. By having sufficient liquidity, banks can meet their short-term obligations and avoid the risk of significant capital loss. Therefore, a high current ratio can contribute to a better CAR level, because the bank has the ability to maintain sufficient capital. (2) Relationship between current assets and capital: A high current ratio indicates that the bank has sufficient current assets to meet its short-term obligations. In many cases, these current assets can be in the form of customer deposits or short-term loans to customers. When banks use short-term loans as a funding source to provide long-term credit, the quality of those assets becomes important. In this case, a high current ratio can help banks maintain high quality assets, which in turn can improve the quality of bank capital and CAR.

Second, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. Current ratio and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) are two financial ratios used to analyze the financial health of companies, including banking companies. A high current ratio tends to have a positive influence on DER in banking. When banking companies have a high current ratio, this indicates that they have sufficient liquidity to meet their short-term obligations, including short-term debt payments. With strong liquidity, banks can reduce the risk of debt repayment failure and have better access to short-term funding sources. In this case, banks may tend to use more debt (leverage) to obtain the additional funding needed. However, it is important to remember that a DER that is too high can also increase financial risk company, including the risk of bankruptcy if debt levels become unmanageable or if the company faces significant financial stress. Therefore, banking companies must maintain a balance between sufficient liquidity and wise use of debt to avoid excessive risk. In general, the influence of the Current ratio on DER in banking is that a high Current ratio tends to be associated with a higher DER, because strong liquidity allows banks to use more debt to fund their operations. However, decisions regarding appropriate debt levels must consider risk factors and the company's overall financial condition.

Third, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. The influence of the current ratio on DPR in banking can vary depending on company policy and strategy. However, in general, there are several things to consider: (1) Liquidity: A high current ratio indicates that the company has sufficient liquidity to meet its short-term obligations. In this case, banks may have more flexibility to pay dividends to shareholders without compromising their liquidity needs. Therefore, a high current ratio can potentially support a higher DPR. (2) Growth and Investment: If banks

plan to expand or invest in the near future, they may need to keep a large portion of their net profits to finance these plans. In this case, a lower current ratio can provide the necessary funds for the investment, and therefore a lower DPR. (3) Regulations and Capital Requirements: Banking is subject to strict regulations and capital requirements. In some cases, regulators may set limits or conditions regarding dividend payments. If banks must comply with certain capital requirements or prioritize meeting capital needs, their DPR may be affected, regardless of the current ratio.

Fourth, financial distress. In banking, the current ratio has a significant influence on financial distress. The following are some of the impacts of the current ratio on financial distress in banking: (1) Liquidity: Current A low ratio can indicate a liquidity problem, namely the company's inability to meet its short-term obligations. If banks face difficulties in meeting current obligations such as loan or deposit payments due, this can cause financial distress. (2) Solvency: A low current ratio can also indicate a solvency problem, namely the company's ability to pay its long-term obligations. If banks are unable to meet their long-term obligations, such as long-term loan payments, this can cause financial distress. (3) Asset Quality: A low current ratio can also reflect problems in the quality of banking assets. If a bank has a lot of illiquid or risky assets, such as problematic loans or bad investments, this can affect the current ratio and cause financial distress. Financial Distress in banking can have serious consequences, including the inability to fulfill obligations to customers and investors, a decrease in public trust, and even the possibility of bankruptcy. Therefore, it is important for banks to monitor and maintain a healthy current ratio to avoid the risk of financial distress.

Fifth, share prices. In banking, the current ratio can have an influence on share prices. The following are several ways how the current ratio can influence stock prices in banking: (1) Level of investor confidence: Current A high ratio indicates that the company has a strong ability to meet its short-term obligations. This reflects the company's financial stability and can increase investor confidence. Investors tend to be more interested in investing in companies with a healthy current ratio, which in turn can encourage share prices to increase. (2) Potential to face emergency liquidity: A high current ratio indicates that the company has enough current assets to deal with emergency situations that require immediate liquidity. This can provide protection for investors in the event of market instability or other unexpected events. As a result, investors may be more inclined to buy shares of companies with high current ratios, which can have a positive impact on share prices. (3) Perception of risk management: A healthy current ratio can also reflect good risk management in banking companies. If a company can manage its liquidity well, investors will have a better perception of the company's ability to face economic and financial challenges. This can increase investor confidence and have a positive impact on share prices.

Sixth, net profit. The effect of the current ratio on net profit in banking can vary depending on several factors. Below are several possible influences that could occur: (1) Liquidity and smooth operations: A high current ratio indicates a high level of liquidity, which means the bank has enough current assets to meet its short-term obligations. In this case, banks will be better prepared to deal with daily funding needs, such as withdrawing funds by customers. With good liquidity, banks can operate their business smoothly and generate stable income, which in turn can contribute to higher net profits. (2) Credit risk management: Current A high ratio can also be an indicator that a bank has a strict credit policy and is careful in providing loans to customers. This can reduce credit risks experienced by banks, such as the possibility of failed credit payments or bad credit. By

reducing credit risk, banks can maintain higher net profits. (3) Operational costs: Although current A high ratio can indicate good liquidity, too many unproductive current assets can also affect net profit. If banks hold too many current assets that do not generate income, such as excessive cash in safe deposit boxes, this can lead to higher operating costs. High operational costs can reduce banking net profits. (4) Effect of interest rates: Banking is a business that is greatly affected by interest rates. A high current ratio can indicate that a bank has a lot of cash or current assets invested in money market instruments with low interest rates. When interest rates rise, the interest income from such investments may also increase. However, when interest rates are low, interest income may decline, which could negatively impact net income.

Seventh, productive financing. The influence of the current ratio on productive financing in banking can vary depending on economic conditions and the bank's business strategy. However, in general, a healthy current ratio can have a positive influence on productive financing. The following are some possible influences: (1) Ability to meet obligations: A high current ratio indicates that the bank has sufficient liquid assets to meet its short-term obligations. This gives confidence to lenders or investors that the bank can fulfill its obligations and pay loans on time. As a result, banks may find it easier to obtain additional financing for productive activities. (2) Level of investor confidence: Investors tend to look at current ratio as an important financial indicator in evaluating bank performance. A healthy current ratio reflects the bank's ability to manage liquidity and face financial risks. This can increase investor confidence and make the bank more attractive to them. With a high level of trust, banks can more easily obtain productive financing from investors. (3) Ability to provide loans: A good current ratio can increase a bank's ability to provide productive loans to its customers. With sufficient liquidity, banks can channel funds to sectors that need financing, such as small and medium businesses, the agricultural sector, industry and other productive sectors. This can provide a positive impact on economic growth and sectors that receive financing from banks.

Eighth, bond rating. In the banking industry, the current ratio can be one of the factors considered by rating agencies in determining bank bond ratings. Bond ratings reflect the credit risk inherent in the financial instrument. The influence of the current ratio on bond ratings in banks can vary depending on economic conditions and the banking industry as a whole. However, in general, having a high current ratio can provide a positive signal to rating agencies, indicating that the bank has sufficient liquidity to meet its short-term obligations. A high current ratio indicates that the bank has more current assets compared to its current liabilities. This can provide confidence to rating agencies that the bank has a good ability to repay its bonds at maturity. On the other hand, if the current ratio is low, it means that the bank has limited liquidity and may face difficulties in meeting its short-term obligations. This can affect the rating agency's assessment and result in a reduction in the bond rating.

Ninth, Return On Assets/ROA. The influence of the current ratio on ROA in banking can vary depending on the situation and business conditions of the bank. However, in general, a healthy current ratio can have a positive influence on ROA. The following are some possible influences: (1) Sufficient liquidity: A high current ratio indicates that the bank has sufficient liquid assets to meet its short-term obligations. With sufficient liquidity, banks can manage liquidity risks well and avoid funding shortages that could disrupt bank operations. This can contribute to operational efficiency and increase ROA. (2) Risk control: A healthy current ratio reflects the bank's ability to manage financial risks. Banks with a high current ratio tend to have more flexibility to deal with unexpected events or uncertainty in

the market. With good risk control, banks can reduce the risk of significant losses and increase ROA. (3) Third party trust: A high current ratio can increase the trust of third parties, such as customers and investors. Customers will be more likely to trust banks that have sufficient liquidity to meet their financial needs, and investors will see this as a positive financial indicator. In the long term, this can increase bank business activities, asset growth, and ultimately, ROA.

Tenth, Return On Equity/ROE. The influence of the current ratio on ROE in banking can vary depending on the company's financial and operational conditions. However, in general, a high current ratio can have a positive influence on ROE. Here are some reasons why this might happen: (1) Adequate liquidity: A high current ratio indicates that the company has adequate liquidity to meet its short-term obligations. This can reduce the risk of failure to pay obligations which could have a negative impact on ROE. Thus, companies with a high current ratio may be better able to maintain stable profits and ROE. (2) Ability to provide loans: Banking is a sector that is highly dependent on providing loans and raising funds. With a high current ratio, the company can demonstrate the ability to provide more loans to its customers. This can increase interest income and net profit, which in turn can improve ROE.

Eleventh, stock returns. The following are some of the effects that may arise from a high current ratio on stock returns in banking: (1) Investor confidence: A high current ratio indicates that the company has sufficient liquidity to meet its short-term obligations. This can increase investors' confidence in the company, because they feel confident that the company is able to manage its finances well. High trust can be achieved encourage demand for company shares, which in turn can increase stock returns. (2) Minimize risks: In the banking industry, liquidity risk is one of the main risks faced. By having a high current ratio, a company can reduce liquidity risks that may arise due to the inability to meet its short-term obligations. In the long term, this can reduce the risk felt by investors and has the potential to increase stock returns. (3) Growth capability: A high current ratio can also strengthen the company's financial position and provide flexibility in facing growth opportunities. Companies with a good current ratio are more likely to get access to easier and cheaper funding sources. In the long term, company growth can increase share value and produce higher returns for shareholders.

Twelfth, Yield to Maturity/YTM. The relationship between current ratio and YTM in banking may not be very direct or clear. The current ratio focuses more on the company's short-term assets and liabilities, while the YTM is related to the rate of return on investment in the financial market. However, there are several factors that can influence the relationship between these two things: (1) Credit risk: A high current ratio indicates that the company has good financial ability to pay its short-term obligations. This can strengthen the company's financial image in the eyes of investors and reduce credit risk. In this case, a bank with a high current ratio may be considered a safer entity and may offer bonds with a lower YTM. (2) Liquidity risk: Banks with low current ratios may face higher liquidity risks. This can influence investors' perceptions of the risk of investing in the company's bonds or debentures. In this situation, to attract investor interest, the company may need to offer a higher YTM on its bonds.

Mapping Research Topics around Factors that Influence the Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using Library Research

Based on a Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 1 factor that influences the current ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely capital policy. Capital policy can affect a bank's current ratio in several ways: first, additional capital. If a bank takes a policy to increase its capital, either through issuing new shares or additional loans, the

current ratio can increase. This is because with additional capital, the bank's total current assets can increase, while short-term liabilities remain stable. Thus, the current ratio increases. Second, reducing capital. On the other hand, if a bank takes a policy to reduce its capital, for example by buying back shares or paying off loans, the current ratio may decrease. Reducing capital will reduce total current assets, while short-term liabilities remain the same. As a result, the current ratio decreases. Third, the use of capital for investment. If a bank uses its capital to make long-term investments, such as acquisitions or infrastructure development, this can have a negative impact on the current ratio. This is because long-term investments reduce bank liquidity in the long run short, while short-term liabilities remain the same. As a result, the current ratio decreases. In managing capital policies, banks must strike a balance between maintaining adequate capital levels to meet regulatory requirements and maintaining a healthy current ratio. A low current ratio can indicate high liquidity risk, while a current ratio that is too high can indicate inefficient use of capital. Therefore, banks need to pay careful attention to their capital policies to maintain the right balance between liquidity and capital adequacy.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the current ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2013 to 2023 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 33 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results regarding current ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking, divided into 6 clusters and 92 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 28 topics, cluster 2 consists of 25 topics, cluster 3 consists of 16 topics, cluster 4 consists of 12 topics, cluster 5 consists of 10 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 1 topic. Third, based on the mapping of the Library Research study, there are 12 topics related to the influence of the current ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, financial distress, stock prices, net profit, productive financing, bond rating, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, stock returns, and Yield to Maturity/YTM. And There is 1 topic related to the determinants of the current ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: capital policy.

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